

ACTIVITY OF THE INTERNATIONAL PHILARMONY IN THE
DEVELOPMENT OF MUSICAL ART

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Annotation. This article talks about the history of music and its development, its origin, when and where it appeared, the role of Philharmonic societies (*in the case of the Luxembourg Philharmonic*), and the history of its development.

Key words: music, formative period, Philharmonic, ticket, website, concert, hall.

*“Music is measured and compared with nothing
has an incomparable divine influence”*

Shavkat Mirziyoyev

President of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

As a person matures, he needs many things. Let's say his needs in his daily life: after doing mental work, he should rest and relax, have a regular 3-course meal, including physical work. In addition to them, a person should read more and communicate more on interesting topics to train and enrich his mental potential and spirituality. There is another strange aspect of man, which also needs food. This is his mental state, his spiritual side. Mentality is one of the most important aspects of a person's ability to manifest many possibilities and ensure self-confidence. All abstract feelings of a person originate from his psyche. Music is the food of the soul.

The art of music (from Greek means "the art of the spirits of inspiration". The art of sound. [1:1]) appeared in ancient times. People who lived in the period of the primitive community system were able to distinguish between musical and noisy sounds in nature, learned to sing, and created the first musical instruments. Until now, these words have been improved, and their performance styles have also developed and enriched. People who have musical abilities among the people enriched the art of music by creating wonderful musical works.

When and where did music appear? How was its formation and development? What factors were important in the emergence of musical art? It is known that such questions have interested mankind since ancient times. In this regard, different peoples have created various narratives and legends, fairy tales and epics in the form of oral creation. The primary ideas that the art of music appeared in this world by the power of God who created it were also put forward.

If we focus on Greek mythology, in their view, music is theology, and they used it to praise the gods and express their praises through music (song). For example, "peana" and "noma" - Apollo, "parfenii" and "yupingi" - Artemis, "diphyrambus", "iobacchus" and "phallic" - Dionysus, "iula" - Demeter, "metroa" - Cybele and another there were songs performed in honor of a number of gods. Besides him, there were also separate gods of music. In our Asian region, there are also assumptions that music is considered a part of medicine. Shamans played various chiltons and drum-like musical instruments to bring back the evil spirits that had entered people.

So, music has been accompanying humanity for centuries. As the world view of mankind became richer, its music also changed. Humanity has adapted music to itself in every era. Therefore, everyone understands music differently. For someone, music is a collection of simple sounds, for others it is an example of a physical phenomenon, for someone it is an integral part of life. His place in our life is immeasurable. In my opinion, there is no one who does not listen to music. The reason is that there is no soul that music has not been able to open its doors. Just as a person is thirsty for water, so his soul is thirsty for music.

It may or may not be felt by a person. It fills the mental energy base and calms the nervous system after physical and mental work. This feature affects not only humanity, but also representatives of the animal world. In ancient times, people used the sounds of music to hunt and tame wild animals. It can be seen that music is important in human life. It is very important to preserve it, to reorganize it, to create and restore it in accordance with the spirit of today. It is no exaggeration to say that new views, new reforms and a new musical culture have entered the new Uzbekistan. In addition, in this regard, it is important to assess the special place of musical culture in spiritual life, to direct its power of influence towards the idea of independence, and to realize that it is its main criterion. According to this principle, shifts are observed in our cultural life today. We would not be mistaken if we say that the thoughts of the creators are directed towards these principles.

Currently, a lot of work is being carried out aimed at widely promoting the art of music, instilling its essence into the minds and hearts of the young generation, helping residents spend their free time effectively, and preserving the musical heritage of nations. One of them was the project of Cultural Centers "Kuylar jilosi". In the yard of the cultural centers, people's favorite tunes are played every morning on the loudspeakers. On this day, organizations that have been singing music to everyone are operating in Uzbekistan and around the world. One such important organization is the Philharmonic. This organization is important not only in Uzbekistan, but also in the whole world.

Philharmonia (from Greek. phileo - love and harmonia-harmony; "I love harmony") is the name of concert organizations in some countries. It was established in the second half of the XIXth century in European and American cities. The first philharmonic societies mainly promoted symphonic music. In most countries, the philharmonic is a state organization whose mission is to promote high artistic musical works and the skills of accomplished performers. Along with music, it sometimes also shows types of pop art (stage dancing, artistic reading, etc.). Large musical groups (orchestra, choir, etc.), various ensembles, solo singers and musicians work in Philharmonia.

Residents mainly visit the Philharmonic to spend their time productively and pleasantly. That is, they enjoy various concert programs. Basically, theatrical concerts begin with powerful, lively and public performances. Let's get acquainted with the Philharmonic organizations that have their own importance in the world.

One of them is the Luxembourg Philharmonic. This Philharmonic is a large concert hall named after Josephine Charlotte, the wife of Grand Duke Jean. Local people call it "Luxembourg Philharmonic". It is located in the district of Kirchberg and was opened in 2005, six months before the death of Duke Jean's wife.

The decision to build a new concert hall was made by the Luxembourg Parliament in 1996. The following year, according to the results of the international competition, the project presented by the French architect Christian de Porzampard was selected for implementation. Construction began in 2002 and lasted three years. On June 26, 2005, the hall opened its doors to the public for the first time. The opening of the hall led to a week-long festival in which about 750 musicians took part and the number of visitors exceeded 15,000. As part of the festival, the world premiere of Krzysztof Penderecki's Eighth Symphony was performed by the Luxembourg Philharmonic Orchestra, for which the new hall became the main concert venue.

A unique technology was used in the construction of the Philharmonic, as a result of which there are excellent acoustics, and the sound of the orchestra can be heard equally well in any corner of the hall. Thanks to such acoustics, the listeners feel as if they are surrounded by the members of the orchestra. In addition to the main hall, the Luxembourg Philharmonic is ready to welcome guests in a smaller hall (313 people). The Philharmonic also has a children's hall where performances are suitable for children.

Luxemburg Philharmonic has a score of 3,49 among TOP attractions in Pfaffenthal, Luxembourg. Even the architectural design chosen for the Philharmonic building literally breathes music. This feeling is embodied in 823 white steel columns arranged in four rows.

From the outside, the building looks like a harp or even an organ (due to the many columns). The acoustics are excellent. There is a good restaurant at the back of the building and next to it is a modern art museum.

About the price and procedure for obtaining tickets to the Philharmonic:

- Individual ticket sales for subscription concerts are usually announced and begin 2 months before the concert date. The exception is if the date falls on a weekend, holiday or school holiday, the start date of ticket sales will be changed.
- Exact dates will be announced on the Philharmonic's website and in its monthly programs. The sale always starts at 10:00.
- Cashiers are open Monday through Friday from 10:00 a.m. to 6:30 p.m. You can get answers to questions by phone (+352) 26 32 26 32
- One-time attendees aged 30 and under are entitled to a 40% discount on individual tickets for Philharmonic concerts, unless otherwise specified.

- Cashier service is closed on Saturdays and Sundays.
- There is an app called Phil30 through which tickets can be purchased at affordable prices.
- Seats can be viewed and reserved using the app from 10:00 a.m. to 1 hour before the start of the event.

The repertoire of the Philharmonic is constantly published on the official website of the Philharmonic along with ticket prices.

The above notes and information were only about the Luxembourg Philharmonic. There are many such organizations around the world. All of them aim to develop the art of music and dance in the country, to satisfy the cultural needs of the population, to attract them to cultural life, to find and encourage young artists, to promote the country's music and dance, theater art and many other arts. serves to promote widely abroad.

At the same time as the human heart feels a thirst for beauty, it is nourished and formed by the environment of beauty. Music is art, and art is a miracle. There are such special places of the heart and brain that can be accessed only through the means of art," said the oriental thinker Abu Ali Ibn Sina.

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